

Investigation on the impact of potassium and mild transport limitations on the pyrolysis behavior of beech wood and its macrocomponents

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ABSTRACT

The existing pyrolysis mechanisms for biomass rarely take into consideration certain feedstock-specific features, such as the interaction between macrocomponents or the influence of inorganic species. This research delves deeper into the impact of potassium (K) and mild transport limitations on the pyrolytic behavior of beech wood and its macrocomponents (modeled in the present work by cellulose, xylan, and alkali lignin). Special attention was given to the interactions between macrocomponents in the beech wood in comparison to their individual behavior. A combination of experimental techniques has been applied, which enabled investigation on (I) the devolatilization behavior and heats of reaction through thermogravimetric analysis/differential scanning calorimetry (TGA/DSC), (II) the *in-situ* evolution of functional groups in the solid thanks to diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy (DRIFTS), and (III) the pyrolysis products composition by means of pyrolysis gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (Py-GC/MS). The interactions between the macrocomponents were addressed via a five parallel-reaction kinetic model and its comparison with the commercial model compounds. Detailed information about the pyrolysis mechanistic pathways was extracted from the *in-situ* DRIFTS characterization by means of a two dimensional perturbation correlation infrared spectroscopy (2D-PCIS) analysis. This technique revealed strong impact of K on cellulose, xylan, and beech wood behavior during the pyrolysis process, enhancing ring opening and dehydration reactions and hindering the formation of anhydrosugars. However, pyrolysis products of beech wood were dominated by those of lignin. It is shown that a detailed understanding of the mechanistic pathways of wood pyrolysis requires not only the understanding of the behavior of its macrocomponents but also of their interaction at a multiple level.

1. Introduction

Lignocellulosic biomass is mainly formed by three biopolymers, namely cellulose (40–60 wt%), hemicellulose (10–30 wt%), and lignin (10–25 wt%) [1,2], as well as of varying amounts of extractives and inorganic species. Cellulose is the most extensively investigated macrocomponent in biomass from both the formation and structure point of view, as well as from the thermochemical decomposition perspective. Cellulose is built upon β 1→4 linked D-glucose monomers and is the main component in plant cell walls [3]. The glucose monomers

form linear chain polymers with 1000–10000 glucose units [4], which arrange in a lattice structure of elementary fibrils of 1.5–3.5 nm in diameter [3,5–7]. The rigidity and mechanical strength of the elementary fibrils is provided by the intra- and inter-chain hydrogen bonding which, together with other intermolecular forces, lead to different degrees of crystallinity [3,4]. Hemicelluloses are non-cellulosic, branched polysaccharides with β 1→4 linked backbones of glucose, mannose, or xylose, with their main function being to tie the cellulose microfibril bundles, increasing the strength of the plant cell walls [3,8]. Terrestrial

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plant hemicelluloses include xyloglucans, xylans, mannans, and glucmannans with significant differences in structural and physicochemical properties [8]. Xylan is typically used as representative component of hardwood hemicelluloses [9,10]. Lignin is a highly heterogeneous aromatic macromolecule whose composition and structure varies significantly among species and growing conditions. It provides strength to the plant cell walls, as well as hydrophobicity and resistance to microbial activity [3,11].

The chemical and physical structure of biomass make it a highly complex material. This has hindered the development of high-fidelity and feedstock-independent thermochemical conversion models, capable of providing a detailed description of the multiscale chemical and physical phenomena involved [3]. In the literature, detailed mechanistic models are available that describe the thermochemical conversion of cellulose or simpler glucose-based compounds (e.g., [12–20]), representative hemicelluloses (e.g., [21]), and lignin (e.g., [22]). However, these models, with potentially hundreds of reactions and species, may become too costly to be implemented in multi-dimensional reactor models, accounting for a detailed description of the physical phenomena involved and their interaction with chemistry at a multi-scale level [23–26]. A semi-detailed pyrolysis model developed by the group of Ranzi and Faravelli at the Politecnico di Milano and further improved, both internally and externally [27–31], has been successfully implemented in particle and reactor models [32–35], showing a good balance between the offered level of detail and the derived complexity of the numerical problem.

The current knowledge of the pyrolytic behavior of biomass macrocomponents is included, with different degrees of accuracy, into existing detailed and semi-detailed pyrolysis models. However, these models do not account for the potential impact of relevant feedstock features, determined to a significant level by the multi-scale and hierarchical structure of biomass. These include the interaction between macrocomponents, dependent on the feedstock chemical and physical morphology; the impact of biomass physical structure [36,37] via e.g., the occurrence of heterogeneous secondary reactions [38,39]; or the influence of inorganic species. Especially the last two may result in important synergistic effects of the pyrolysis process [40,41]. The absence of these phenomena in current biomass pyrolysis models hinders the development of feedstock-independent approaches with a wide range of applicability in terms of physico-chemical interactions [3].

In previous studies, the combined influence of alkali species and intra-particle transport-limited regimes has been investigated with the use of thermally thick wood particles [40–43]. However, it was not possible to determine how each biomass macrocomponent was affected or contributed to the global biomass behavior. To help answer this question, the present work investigates the impact of inorganic species under limited influence of transport limitations (mild transport limitations) on cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin, as well as on beech wood. Commercial model compounds, namely Avicel PH-105 microcrystalline cellulose, xylan (typically used as representative of hardwood hemicellulose [44], and alkali lignin (commonly used as representative of biomass lignin [44]) have been employed. These compounds cannot fully replicate the behavior of the native macrocomponents in biomass since they do not maintain their original morphology due to the extraction procedure [45]; they include extrinsic compounds such as inorganics; and they represent only one of the several species that may be present, as it is the case for hemicellulose and lignin. Therefore, special care is needed when comparing the behavior of these compounds with the parent beech wood. Nevertheless, they still enable the investigation on the impact of inorganic species and transport limitations during the pyrolysis process. To overcome part of these limitations, some techniques have appeared in the past years that employ less invasive pretreatment procedures, such as native mixing [46]. Although in this scenario quantitative comparisons are also not possible and the potential impact of the pretreatments on the composition and physical structure of the components continues to pose a threat to the

results, these are widely accepted due to its better representation of the interaction between components [47,48]. In the present work, a combination of thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), coupled with differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), *in-operando* diffuse reflectance Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (DRIFTS), and pyrolysis coupled with gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (Py-GC/MS) has been selected to perform the experimental analyses. Despite the different experimental conditions achieved by the selected techniques, especially regarding heating rate, this combination has already been successfully used for the investigation of the initial decomposition pathway of cellulose [20] and hemicellulose [49]. The several layers of data generated by this approach allow for an in-depth analysis of the pyrolysis process. This, combined with the different transport regimes and the modification of the feedstock by either washing or doping with potassium, results in a novel approach to the study of the effects these variables have on the pyrolysis of beech wood and its macrocomponents. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first study where the influence of inorganic species on the pyrolysis behavior of woody biomass and its macrocomponents has been investigated *in-operando* by means of diffuse reflectance Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (DRIFTS).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Biomass and components

Cellulose (Avicel PH-105 microcrystalline cellulose 0.020 mm, SERVA Electrophoresis GmbH), commercial xylan from beech wood (Sigma Aldrich), alkali lignin (Sigma Aldrich), and beech wood were used in the present study. For each material, three levels of potassium (K) content were targeted by washing and doping the raw samples. Pure cellulose, as received, had a negligible content in inorganic species (see Table 1). Hence, it was doped with two different concentrations of K by soaking it in aqueous solutions (with deionized water) of KCl under continuous stirring for at least 24 h. After this, the doped samples were filtered with glass microfiber filters (IDL GmbH & Co. KG) and dried for at least 8 h at 106 °C.

Xylan, as received, contained already a high amount of inorganic species, derived from the extraction methodology. Hence, to target the two desired levels of K, it was washed (with deionized water) and doped (the original xylan, with an aqueous solution of KCl) under continuous stirring for at least 24 h. Due to the higher solubility of xylan in water in comparison to cellulose, filtering to separate the main solid fraction from the solution was not possible. Therefore, water was removed by drying at 106 °C during several days, until no significant mass variation was detected. Most of the inorganic species present in the raw xylan remained in the washed sample as well (see X-W and X in Table 1). Analogously, most of the added K remained in the xylan after the doping procedure, yielding the highest K concentration among all samples.

Alkali lignin (Sigma Aldrich) was washed and doped (the original lignin) following the same method previously introduced.

Beech wood spheres (25 mm in diameter) were twice washed with deionized water in vacuum during 24 h. KCl doping was performed, as for the aforementioned samples, after the washing procedure, to remove other inorganic species. The wood spheres were then milled for the experimental analyses performed in the present work.

Ash content and inorganic elemental analysis of all samples are shown in Table 1. Inorganic elemental composition was characterized in an ICP-OES (inductively coupled plasma - optical emission spectrometer, Varian 720-ES), after digestion in a microwave (Multiwave 3000, from Anton Paar) with HNO₃ and H₂O₂.

Table 1

Ash (wt%, in dry basis) and inorganic species content (mg/kg) of cellulose (C), xylan (X), lignin (L), and beech wood (B). K1 and K2 represent the two doping levels for the cellulose samples, W represents the washed samples, and K represents the doped samples other than cellulose with the highest K content.

	Ash (wt%)	K (mg kg ⁻¹)	Ca (mg kg ⁻¹)	Na (mg kg ⁻¹)	S (mg kg ⁻¹)
C	0.01 ± 0.00	19 ± 8	n.d.	n.d.	25 ± 2
C-K1	0.06 ± 0.02	426 ± 43	n.d.	n.d.	12 ± 3
C-K2	0.37 ± 0.10	3426 ± 293	n.d.	n.d.	7 ± 0.1
X-W	3.32 ± 0.06	246 ± 22	4100 ± 270	14393 ± 445	142 ± 10
X	3.26 ± 0.14	236 ± 16	5916 ± 140	14095 ± 368	159 ± 4
X-K	6.72 ± 0.16	32029 ± 278	3126 ± 15	12750 ± 158	116 ± 1
L-W	1.04 ± 0.11	450 ± 80	n.d.	3072 ± 256	12751 ± 402
L	2.44 ± 0.02	688 ± 20	n.d.	6952 ± 118	16037 ± 99
L-K	2.34 ± 0.16	11783 ± 1520	n.d.	4196 ± 187	13828 ± 602
B-W	0.21 ± 0.01	379 ± 41	732 ± 6	21 ± 3	81 ± 3
B	0.31 ± 0.01	771 ± 133	750 ± 50	16 ± 8	94 ± 4
B-K	1.05 ± 0.01	7519 ± 258	428 ± 42	17 ± 6	81 ± 12

(a) Devolatilization rate of the cellulose samples with 5 mg, 5 mg with lid, and 20 mg.

(b) Cellulose (C)

(c) Cellulose doped with the lowest level of K (C-K1)

(d) Cellulose doped with the highest level of K (C-K2)

Fig. 1. TGA and DSC analyses of pure cellulose, cellulose doped with the low level of K (C-K1), and cellulose doped with the high level of K (C-K2) obtained at 10 °Cmin⁻¹ using 20 mg of initial sample when not indicated otherwise.

(a) Devolatilization rate of the samples with 5 mg, 5 mg with lid, and 20 mg.

(b) Xylan (X)

(c) Washed xylan (X-W)

(d) K-doped xylan (X-K)

Fig. 2. TGA and DSC analyses of pure xylan (X), washed xylan (X-W), and xylan doped with K (X-K), obtained at 10 °Cmin⁻¹ using 20mg of initial sample when not indicated otherwise.

2.2. Thermogravimetric analysis

Investigation of the devolatilization behavior of the prepared samples was performed under N₂ atmosphere in a Linseis STA PT1600 thermogravimetric analyzer (TGA) with differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The thermal cycles applied consisted in heating the sample from room temperature to 600 °C with heating rates of 2.5, 5, and 10 °C·min⁻¹. The temperature resolution of the device is 0.01 °C. Sample masses of 5 mg and 20 mg were used. The purpose was to establish one intrinsic pyrolysis regime, free of transport limitations (5 mg), and one transport-limited regime with mild intra-particle (20 mg) transport limitations. External transport limitations were also imposed by covering the crucible with a lid during some experiments using 5 mg of sample. To ensure repeatability, each experiment was repeated three times.

From the TGA curves, the devolatilization rate is derived according to Eq. (1):

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = -\frac{1}{m_i - m_f} \frac{dm}{dt} \quad (1)$$

where α is the conversion, m_i is the initial dried mass before the pyrolysis process, m_f is the final mass of the char after the pyrolysis process, and m is the mass of the sample at each time step.

2.2.1. Differential scanning calorimetry

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was used to analyze the thermal behavior of the samples in a controlled environment during pyrolysis. This method compares the behavior of the sample with that of an inert reference to determine the heat absorbed or released during the pyrolysis process.

(a) Devolatilization rate of the samples with 5 mg, 5 mg with lid, and 20 mg of initial sample.

(b) Lignin (L)

(c) Washed lignin (L-W)

(d) K-doped lignin (L-K)

Fig. 3. TGA and DSC analyses of pure lignin (L), washed lignin (L-W), and lignin doped with K (L-K), obtained at 10 °C·min⁻¹ using 20 mg of initial sample when not indicated otherwise.

2.2.2. Kinetic modeling

Thermogravimetric analysis enables the examination of global reaction rates during pyrolysis. Many reaction models have been proposed over the years for solid-state reactions of diverse complexity, depending on the material studied and the thermal process applied. Approaches based on avoiding to commit to a certain reaction model (model-free) are popular due to their simplicity and the robustness of their results. Nevertheless, they are significantly influenced by the device used and the thermal program applied. These so-called model-free methods, such as Flynn–Wall–Ozawa (FWO) [50], shown in Eq. (2) or Kissinger–Akahira–Sunose (KAS) [51], shown in Eq. (3), use constant heating rates (β) and approximations of the resulting temperature integral to extract kinetic parameters from experiments performed at several heating rates, with results that are widely accepted [52–56]. In these equations, A represents the pre-exponential factor, E the activation energy and $g(\alpha)$ the integral form of the kinetic model.

$$\ln(\beta) = \ln\left(\frac{A E}{R g(\alpha)}\right) - 5.331 - 1.052 \frac{E}{R T} \quad (2)$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{\beta}{T^2}\right) = \ln\left(\frac{A R}{E g(\alpha)}\right) - \frac{E}{R T} \quad (3)$$

On the other side, model-fitting approaches are also widely used in the biomass community [56–58]. In the present study, a parallel n th-order reaction model with five reactions (see Eq. (4)) was developed following the approach of Branca et al. [57,59,60]. Cano-Pleite et al. showed that five first-order parallel reactions were enough to accurately describe the pyrolysis of biomass [61]. Branca et al. assigned two first-order reactions to the decomposition of hemicellulose, one first-order reaction to the decomposition of cellulose, and 2 n th-order reactions to the decomposition of lignin [46].

$$\frac{dY_i}{dt} = -A_i \exp\left(\frac{-E_i}{R T}\right) Y_i^{n_i}; \text{ with } i = (1, \dots, 5) \text{ and } Y_i(0) = V_i \quad (4)$$

The mass loss curves obtained from the thermogravimetric analysis were fitted with the model in Eq. (4) using the three heating rates simultaneously to reduce thermal compensation effects and obtain more

(a) Devolatilization rate of the samples with 5 mg, 5 mg with lid, and 20 mg.

(b) Raw beech wood (B)

(c) Washed beech wood (B-W)

(d) K-doped beech wood (B-K)

Fig. 4. TGA and DSC analyses of raw beech wood (B), washed beech wood (B-W), and beech wood doped with K (B-K), obtained at 10 °Cmin⁻¹ using 20 mg of initial sample when not indicated otherwise.

representative results for each sample [62]. The obtained parameters included activation energy E_i , pre-exponential factor A_i , reaction order n_i , and relative contribution of each reaction (and hence pseudocomponent) to devolatilization V_i . Y_i is the mass fraction of pseudocomponent being devolatilized in each reaction. The objective function of the optimization problem is defined in Eq. (5).

$$F = \sum_{j=(1,\dots,M)} \frac{\sum_{i=(1,\dots,N_j)} (Y_{ij})_{sim} - (Y_{ij})_{exp}}{N_j}^2 \quad (5)$$

In this expression, N_j is the number of datapoints in a given experiment and M is the number of heating rates studied for a given sample. To solve the optimization problem, the differential equation describing the reaction progress (Eq. (4)) is discretized using an implicit Euler approach and integrated into the optimization problem as nonlinear constraints. Mass balances are ensured with additional constraints. The optimization problem is solved using CasADi [63] to efficiently compute derivatives based on algorithmic differentiation that are then

Table 2
Heats of reaction of the 20 mg samples with a heating rate of 10 °Cmin⁻¹.

	H_r (kJ/kg)	m_{char} (mg)	m_0 (mg)	char yield (wt%)
C	388.61	0.96	20.25	4.74
CK1	115.48	1.48	19.86	7.45
CK2	-111.4	1.97	20.02	9.84
L-W	-228.98	9.49	19.76	48.03
L	-290.22	9.96	19.99	49.82
L-K	-709.16	9.94	20.11	49.43
X-W	-533.91	5.05	19.92	25.35
X	-422.76	5.15	19.93	25.84
X-K	-634.19	5.78	19.95	28.97
B-W	-80.22	2.19	19.91	11.00
B	38.83	2.74	19.85	13.80
B-K	-369.59	3.83	19.77	19.37

given to IPOPT [64] to solve the resulting nonlinear optimization problems.

The accuracy of the model is then compared to the experimental data for the three heating rates, and is expressed as the Normalized

Fig. 5. Results of the five parallel reaction model for beech wood, 20 mg of initial sample. Peak values in the comparisons between experimental and modeled macrocomponents are normalized.

Root Mean Square Deviation (NRMSD) as shown in Eq. (6).

$$NRMSD = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\sum(\alpha_{sim} - \alpha_{exp})^2}{N}}}{\alpha_{max} - \alpha_{min}} \quad (6)$$

2.3. Pyro-GC/MS

Composition of the pyrolysis products was analyzed with pyrolysis gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (Py-GC/MS) using a Frontier Laboratories microfurnace pyrolyser (2020i, Frontier Laboratories, Fukushima, Japan) connected to an Agilent 6890N GC-MS (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA). Approximately 5 mg of finely milled sample underwent pyrolysis at 500°C for 1 min, and the resulting products were introduced into the GC inlet at 250°C . The GC employed an HP-5ms-UI capillary column, following chromatographic conditions outlined by Jiménez-Morillo et al. [65]. Compound assignments were based on diagnostic ions, low-resolution MS, and comparisons with NIST and Wiley libraries.

2.4. Diffuse reflectance Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy

Diffuse reflectance Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (DRIFTS) was performed on a Bruker Vertex 70 V, an off-axis diffuse reflection spectra acquisition device. A high temperature reaction chamber with ZnSe windows was utilized, as well as a temperature controller with a $\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ resolution to perform the heating cycle. Experiments were repeated three times, from room temperature to 600°C and a heating rate of $2.5^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ under a pure nitrogen atmosphere. The infrared (IR) range from 550 to 4000 cm^{-1} was scanned with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and 16 scans per measurement, thus ensuring that the measurement point was located in a $\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ window. A sample mass of 20 mg was used, and background calibrations were performed with KBr every 5 experiments. The required sample mass was determined by the experimental setup. It corresponded to the mild intra-particle transport-limited regime.

Fig. 6. Results of the five parallel reaction model for beech wood, 5 mg of initial sample. Peak values in the comparisons between experimental and modeled macrocomponents are normalized.

2.4.1. Interpretation of the spectra

Temperature-dependent spectra were analyzed by means of two-dimensional perturbation correlation infrared spectroscopy (2D-PCIS), a technique developed based on the work of Noda [66] in the 1990s. It is based on the study of samples altered by any kind of external stimulus or perturbation, such as changes in moisture [67], time [68] or, as it is the case in the present study, temperature [20,69,70]. For the creation of the 2D correlation maps, Peter Lasch's `mat2dcorr` Matlab toolbox was utilized [71].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Thermogravimetric analysis and differential scanning calorimetry

The devolatilization rates ($\frac{da}{dt}$) versus conversion temperature for cellulose, xylan, lignin, and beech wood are presented in Figs. 1(a), 2(a), 3(a), and 4(a), respectively, with a heating rate of $10^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ and for all considered transport regimes. Devolatilization rate curves

at the three heating rates for the 5 mg samples, representing intrinsic conditions (considering negligible transport limitations), are presented in Figure B.1 of the Supplementary Material for comparison purposes. Additionally, the DSC analysis for heating rate of $10^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ and 20 mg of sample, the regime representing mild intra-sample transport limitations, are also shown in Figs. 1, 2, 3, and 4. The results of the integration of the DSC curves to obtain the heat of reaction can be consulted in Table 2. The complexity of using DSC measurements to determine the heat of reaction stems from the fact that many interacting processes that absorb and release heat could affect the obtained values. Nevertheless, for the calculations presented, a correction considering the effect of radiation was implemented, yielding satisfactory results. The characteristic parameters, useful to characterize and compare the different devolatilization curves, were determined analogously to other works in literature [60,72] and are presented in Tables B.1, B.2, and B.3 of the Supplementary Material for the case of $10^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. These parameters include peak and shoulder temperatures T_{peak} and $T_{shoulder}$; mass fractions ($Y = m(t)/m_0$, with $m(t)$ and m_0 being the mass at each

Table 3
Results of the modeling of beech wood using the five parallel reaction model.

		5 mg			20 mg		
		B-W	B	B-K	B-W	B	B-K
Hemicellulose	A1 (min ⁻¹)	1.00×10 ¹³	1.00×10 ¹³	1.00×10 ¹¹	8.96×10 ¹²	1.00×10 ¹³	1.00×10 ¹¹
	E1 (kJ/mol)	157.65	160.00	145.00	160.00	159.13	145.00
	V1	0.15	0.15	0.19	0.15	0.20	0.18
	n1	1.00	0.98	1.01	1.00	1.00	1.01
	A2 (min ⁻¹)	1.00×10 ¹⁴	1.00×10 ¹⁴	2.32×10 ¹²	1.00×10 ¹⁴	9.48×10 ¹³	2.57×10 ¹²
	E2 (kJ/mol)	178.78	178.25	150.00	179.88	180.00	150.00
	V2	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.20
	n2	1.00	0.98	1.01	1.00	1.00	1.01
Cellulose	A3 (min ⁻¹)	1.00×10 ¹⁵					
	E3 (kJ/mol)	203.72	202.56	193.89	203.86	203.60	194.22
	V3	0.44	0.45	0.35	0.45	0.45	0.35
	n3	1.00	1.00	1.01	1.00	1.00	0.99
Lignin	A4 (min ⁻¹)	2.73×10 ⁵	1.00×10 ⁷	6.56×10 ⁵	1.00×10 ⁷	1.00×10 ⁷	6.67×10 ⁵
	E4 (kJ/mol)	75.00	70.81	75.00	70.37	94.38	75.00
	V4	0.030	0.030	0.030	0.047	0.034	0.030
	n4	2.50	2.50	2.50	2.50	2.50	2.50
	A5 (min ⁻¹)	1.00×10 ¹⁴	9.98×10 ¹²	1.32×10 ¹³	1.10×10 ¹³	1.00×10 ¹⁴	1.89×10 ¹³
	E5 (kJ/mol)	160.00	160.00	160.00	160.00	161.12	160.00
	V5	0.11	0.10	0.15	0.11	0.07	0.15
	n5	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
NRMSD α		10.84%	12.03%	13.20%	8.05%	7.92%	8.75%
NRMSD da/dt		6.03%	6.58%	5.17%	4.87%	4.37%	3.41%

Fig. 7. Pyrograms for cellulose (C) and K-doped cellulose (C-K2). Peak identification provided in Table E.21 of the Supplementary Material.

time step and the initial mass) corresponding to the previous peak and shoulder Y_{peak} and $Y_{shoulder}$; peak and shoulder of the devolatilization rate curves: $-(dY/dt)_{peak}$, $-(dY/dt)_{shoulder}$; the characteristic temperatures T_{onset} and T_{offset} ; the temperature differences $T_{shoulder}-T_{onset}$, $T_{peak}-T_{shoulder}$, and $T_{offset}-T_{peak}$; the temperature ranges fwhm (full width of the devolatilization rate curve at the half maximum) and fw (full width of the devolatilization rate curve defined by T_{onset} and T_{offset}); and the final char yield in mass fraction Y_{char} . A graphical explanation of the parameters can be found on the Supplementary Information Figure B.2.

Cellulose (C) devolatilization was recorded as a single event with an endothermic peak approximately coincident with the maximum conversion rate, as can be observed in Figs. 1(a) and 1(b). This behavior is in good agreement with the results reported in the Round-Robin study of Grønli et al. [73] and it is consistent with a global single step reaction [73,74]. Under intrinsic conditions (5 mg), the low level of K-doping (C-K1) led to a shift of T_{peak} to higher temperatures (+22 °C in comparison to cellulose), increase in char yield (1 wt% for C and 3 wt%

Fig. 8. Pyrograms for xylan (X) and K-doped xylan (X-K). Peak identification provided in Table E.21 of the Supplementary Material.

for C-K1), and an overall decrease of the devolatilization rate (see Fig. 1(a)). Higher levels of K-doping (C-K2) shifted back the T_{peak} to lower temperatures (+8 °C in comparison to cellulose), further increased the char yields (7 wt%), and led to devolatilization reactions occurring over a wider temperature range (fwhm of 44 °C and fw of 74 °C for C-K2 and 5 mg versus 33 °C and 56 °C for C and 5 mg). This behavior was consistent for the three transport regimes considered (5 mg, 5 mg with lid, and 20 mg). With higher transport limitations more char was formed. K-doping shifted the heat of reaction from globally endothermic to globally exothermic process (Fig. 1), indicating the predominance of exothermic reactions, including those leading to char formation [40]. The impact of mild transport limitations on cellulose (C) conversion rate was almost negligible, suggesting that devolatilization was controlled by other phenomena, such as the vaporization rate of the formed products. This impact became increasingly relevant with the K-doping degree. In all cases, the highest devolatilization rates were observed for the experiments performed with 5 mg and lid, which represents mild

Fig. 9. Pyrograms for lignin (L) and K-doped lignin (L-K). Peak identification provided in Table E.21 of the Supplementary Material.

Fig. 10. Pyrograms for beech (B) and K-doped beech (B-K). Peak identification provided in Table E.21 of the Supplementary Material.

external transport limitations. For C and C-K1, the lowest conversion rates were observed with 20 mg samples, indicative of intra-particle mild transport limitations. However, the combination of intra-particle transport limitations and high level of doping (C-K2, 20 mg) led to higher conversion rates and lower conversion temperatures in comparison to the intrinsic regime (5 mg). The experiments at these conditions also showed the highest exothermicity among all cellulose cases.

The analysis of xylan, presented in Fig. 2, revealed a more complex conversion, consistent with a global two-stage devolatilization process, mainly attributed to: (I) decomposition leading to the formation of sugars and (II) decomposition via ring opening, with more fragmentation products and char [27,75]. The DSC data correlated well with

these two events, with exothermic peaks that can be linked to the devolatilization curves, while featuring an endothermic peak at around 450 °C, potentially due to changes in the solid char structure. Only small differences were observed in the characteristic parameters of devolatilization between X-W (washed xylan) and X (xylan as received) (Fig. 2(a), Tables B.1, B.2, and B.3 in the Supplementary Material), consistent with the similar composition of both samples due to the unsuccessful washing procedure for xylan (see Table 1). In both cases, the same trend was observed for the different transport regimes: higher devolatilization rates were observed for 5 mg with lid, followed by 20 mg, and 5 mg. The devolatilization rate curves of the samples with 20 mg were slightly shifted to lower temperatures compared to the other transport regimes. K-doping enhanced devolatilization at lower temperatures, to the detriment of the second devolatilization peak, and reduced the temperature range for devolatilization (fwhm and fw). Higher transport limitations also contributed in the same direction as K, with more impact of intra-particle mild transport limitations. The results show the synergistic impact of K and transport limitations on the xylan conversion process.

Lignin, characterized by its complex composition, primarily consisting of three hydroxycinnamyl alcohol monomers with varying degrees of methoxylation [27], exhibited a wider and rather featureless decomposition profile, with mass loss in the entire range of 150–550 °C (see Fig. 3(a)) and a higher devolatilization rate about 300 °C. This was not clearly linked to a particular heat flow event, implying a superposition of both endothermic and exothermic reactions (see Figs. 3(b), 3(c), and 3(d)). A clear exothermic peak was observed at around 400 °C for all cases, but more intensified for K-doped lignin. No clear conclusion could be derived from the impact of washing and K-doping, as well as from the impact of mild transport limitations, on the lignin devolatilization behavior.

The devolatilization rate profile of beech wood showed a main peak between approximately 320–350 °C, depending on the conditions, and a shoulder at lower temperatures, in the region of 250–300 °C (Fig. 4(a)). The former is attributed to the decomposition of cellulose, while the latter is related to the devolatilization of hemicellulose. The contribution of lignin would be distributed along the entire devolatilization range. K-doping significantly shifted the conversion to lower temperatures for all transport regimes in a similar manner and decreased the peak devolatilization rates while increasing those at the shoulder. It also resulted in a higher overlap of the hemicellulose and cellulose devolatilization regions (softer shoulder and lower fwhm, see Tables B.1, B.2, and B.3 in the Supplementary Material). With regard to the DSC results (Figs. 4(b), 4(c), 4(d)), the three samples underwent an endothermic process until approximately 150 °C, most likely linked to drying. This event was followed by a slightly exothermic event at around 300 °C, linked to the beginning of the pyrolysis process and a sharp endothermic peak coinciding with the end of the devolatilization process for B and B-W. K-doping affected significantly the process thermochemistry, resulting in a globally exothermic process, with the peak of heat release located at around 325 °C.

The impact of K on beech cellulose differed from the impact of K on pure cellulose (model compound), with a more clear effect on the first, both looking at the conversion rates and at the process thermochemistry.

3.2. Kinetic analysis

From the TGA and DSC analyses, it is clear that K content and mild transport limitations impacted the pyrolysis chemistry. To better understand this impact, including the synergistic behavior of K and transport limitations on the pyrolysis of beech wood and its macrocomponents, kinetic analyses were performed. Two distinct methodologies were applied. The isoconversional methods KAS and FWO were first used to analyze the impact of K and mild transport limitations on the global kinetics of beech wood pyrolysis and its macrocomponents,

Fig. 11. Evolution of selected FTIR peaks versus pyrolysis temperature.

assuming a global single-step reaction. The results (activation energy and pre-exponential factors) are shown in detail in Section C of the Supplementary Material (Tables C.4 to C.19). The impact of K and transport limitations differed for the different materials. It should be noted that, although meaningful to support with the understanding of the impact of K and mild transport limitations on the global devolatilization behavior of beech wood and its macrocomponents, the global kinetic parameters provided by isoconversional methods are apparent values that agglomerate the different processes occurring in the sample. Hence, they should not be used to derive conclusions about the mechanistic pathways, but they provide kinetic values for the global devolatilization reaction and can contribute to analyze the goodness of model-fitting methods [56]. The quality of the isoconversional analysis was tested by using the obtained kinetic parameters in a first-order reaction model to generate devolatilization curves that could be compared with the experimental data. The best agreement was obtained when using the kinetic parameters correspondent to the conversion $\alpha = 0.5$. The calculated activation energies showed a decrease upon K-doping for cellulose devolatilization under intrinsic regime (5 mg). In the presence of mild transport limitations, both external and internal, K-addition tended to increase the activation energy.

In the case of xylan, the calculated kinetic parameters showed a significant impact of K addition and mild transport limitations on the calculated global kinetic parameters, but the derivation of a clear trend is difficult. The behavior of the samples under external transport limitations differed with respect to internal transport limitations. The highest activation energies were observed for xylan, higher values for the intrinsic regime and intra-sample transport-limited regime. Despite the similar content in inorganic species, the determined activation energies for washed xylan differed significantly from those for xylan under intrinsic and intra-sample transport-limited regimes.

Higher levels of K increased the activation energy for intrinsic conditions and intra-sample transport-limited regimes in lignin. The presence of intra-sample transport limitations also seemed to increase the activation energy for L and L-W. The opposite behavior was though observed for L-K.

For beech wood, the addition of K increased the activation energy in all regimes. Differing behaviors were observed between external and internal transport limitations for B and B-K.

These results show varying impact of K depending on the material and the transport conditions. Therefore, in future kinetic models, where the impact of inorganic species needs to be addressed more consistently, the transport limitations should be also accounted for.

The presented kinetic parameters give information about the impact of K and transport limitations on the devolatilization process. However, as they consider one global single-step reaction for each material, they cannot reproduce accurately the multi-step devolatilization observed nor address in detail the interaction of the different macrocomponents. For this reason, a five parallel-reaction model, with kinetic parameters obtained by model fitting according to Section 2.2.2, was also developed. Cano-Pleite et al. showed that five first-order reactions were enough to properly describe the devolatilization of woody biomass [61]. Branca and Di Blasi also used five reactions (two for hemicellulose, one for cellulose, and two for lignin) to model the behavior of beech wood and the interaction between their macrocomponents [46]. This approach was also followed in the present work. For the case of cellulose and hemicellulose, the targeted reaction order was one, consistent with a devolatilization reaction. For fitting purposes, it was allowed to vary between 0.98 and 1.02.

For exemplification purposes, the experimental and calculated conversion rates, as well as the contribution of the five different reactions,

Fig. 12. 2D-PCIS spectra of cellulose (C) samples.

are shown in Figs. 5(a), 5(d), and 5(g) for B, B-K, and B-W, respectively, with 20 mg of sample and a heating rate of $5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$; and in Figs. 6(a), 6(d), and 6(g) for B, B-K, and B-W, respectively, with 5 mg and a heating rate of $5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The obtained kinetic parameters are summarized in Table 3 for the three levels of K under intrinsic and intra-sample transport-limited conditions. A more detailed view of the results of the fittings of beech wood with different levels of K and transport limitations are provided in Section C of the Supplementary Material.

Higher levels of K reduced the activation energy of the calculated cellulose and hemicellulose fractions (pseudo-cellulose and pseudo-hemicellulose from now on) in beech wood (see Table 3). Intra-particle transport limitations did not impact significantly the kinetic parameters. In Fig. 5, the second and third columns compare the pseudo-hemicellulose and pseudo-cellulose obtained from the model with commercial xylan and cellulose for B, B-W and B-K, using 20 mg of sample. Pseudo-cellulose from B and B-W showed an excellent fitting with K-doped commercial cellulose (C-K1). However, this was not as good for B-K. This could be, in part, due to the different content of inorganic species.

When isolating the reactions linked to hemicellulose and comparing them to the commercial xylan, important differences were observed, especially for the highest heating rate. The bimodal behavior of xylan was reproduced, but the devolatilization of xylan occurred at lower temperatures than for pseudo-hemicellulose. This could be explained by the variability of the composition of hemicellulose in different

lignocellulosic biomasses, as well as by the content in inorganic species in the commercial xylan. The absence of the more stable cellulose and lignin fractions in the commercial xylan could also contribute to the earlier conversion.

3.3. Analysis of pyrolysis products with Py-GC/MS

Pyrolysis coupled with gas chromatography - mass spectrometry (Py-GC/MS) was applied to gain information on the mechanistic pathways, including the impact of K-doping, involved in the pyrolysis of cellulose, xylan, lignin, and beech wood. The sample mass used was approximately 5 mg, which corresponded to the reference intrinsic regime used in the thermogravimetric analysis under slow heating rates. However, in the Py-GC/MS measurements higher heating rates are typically achieved, which may introduce new transport limitations and modify the chemical pathways compared to slow heating rates. Despite this, they provide valuable data to complement other experimental results. In this way, the combination of Py-GC/MS, *in-situ* DRIFTS, and TGA has been previously applied in literature to gain understanding on the detailed mechanistic pathways involved in the pyrolysis of biomass [20, 49].

The total ion chromatograms (TICs) after pyrolysis at $500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ are shown in Figs. 7, 8, 9, and 10 for cellulose, xylan, lignin, and beech wood, respectively. Different behaviors were observed for the samples based on their nature and the presence of K.

Fig. 13. 2D-PCIS spectra of K-doped cellulose (C-K2) samples.

The TIC corresponding to pyrolysis of cellulose (C) and K-doped cellulose (C-K2) showed a major peak attributed to levoglucosan (peak 21, Fig. 7, Table E.21 in Supplementary Material), a well-known marker of cellulose pyrolysis, coming from the cleavage of glycosidic bonds, possibly at non-reducing ends [12,20]. The production of levoglucosan was relevant for both cellulose (C) and K-doped cellulose (C-K2), consistent with the relatively low thermal stability of the glycosidic bonds observed in the DRIFTS measurements (Section 3.4). The formation of products such as 3,5-dihydroxy-6-methyl-4H-pyran-4-one (peak 17), with a high intensity in comparison to other peaks in cellulose, further supports the occurrence of scission of glycosidic bonds and dehydration reactions on the scission products. The formation of 1,4:3,6-dianhydro- α -D-glucopyranose occurred for cellulose (C) pyrolysis (peak 20) but was negligible after pyrolysis of K-doped cellulose (C-K2), suggesting that further dehydration of anhydrosugars was hindered upon K-addition. β -D-Glucopyranose (peak 22) was also observed among the pyrolysis products of both cellulose (C) and K-doped cellulose (C-K2), although the contribution in K-doped cellulose relative to levoglucosan and other compounds was significantly lower. This suggests that β -D-glucose was a relevant intermediate in the pyrolysis of cellulose, with thermal stability even at 500 °C but its presence, at least at high temperatures, for K-doped cellulose was negligible. It has been discussed, for example, that 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), a very important product of pyrolysis as well, may be formed from D-glucose units [76].

Additionally, the TICs revealed derivatives of furans and furfural, present as alcohols, acids, and, to a lesser extent, aldehydes. Furan-derivatives could be formed via ring contraction reactions, such as direct ring contraction or pinacol ring contraction [20,76]. These pathways, with no carbon-carbon bond cleavage in the ring, would most likely lead to the production of C₆ furan derivatives [77]. Furans could also be formed from the cyclization of ring opening products [20,76] such as the Grob fragmentation pathway [77], which mainly leads to the production of C₄ and C₅ furans, or by C(6) hydroxymethyl dissociation, producing 3-furfuraldehyde [20]. The abundance of low molecular weight compounds, indicative of ring fragmentation, highlights the susceptibility of the cellulose ring to cleavage [12,20]. Upon K-doping, most peaks decreased in intensity except some furan-like compounds (peaks 2, 4, 6, 7, 8), including furfural, methyl furans, and furanmethanol, as well as ring fragmentation products. The only peak that clearly increased in relative intensity in C-K2 with respect to C was 2-furanmethanol.

Xylan samples (X, X-K, Fig. 8) yielded very similar TICs, dominated by compounds 50 (2-methylpropanoic acid), 52 (phenol, 2,4-dimethyl-,acetate), 48 (2-methyl-2-propenoic acid), 49 (3-methylbutanal), 6 (furfural), 11 (2,3-dimethyl-pentanal), and 12 (2-furancarboxylic acid), that is, furan derivatives and products of ring fragmentation reactions. The presence of phenolics may be attributed to some lignin still present in the xylan after extraction. This will be covered in detail in Section 3.4.2, due to the presence of a strong signal at

Fig. 14. Evolution of selected FTIR peaks versus pyrolysis temperature.

3640 cm⁻¹, attributed to phenolic OH groups. The most relevant observable differences upon K-addition were the relative decrease of 2-furancarboxylic acid and 1,2-cyclopentanedione. The relatively high abundance of ring fragmentation products versus the low presence of anhydrosugars highlights the preference of ring fragmentation pathway during the pyrolysis of xylan [49].

The lignin-derived TICs (Fig. 9) were well-resolved and showed consistency irrespective of K-addition. Dominant compounds included phenols, methylphenols, and methoxyphenols, hallmark products of lignin depolymerization. The thermal breakdown of lignin primarily releases phenolic compounds, as the aromatic structure of lignin lends itself to such degradation pathways [44].

Beech wood TICs (Fig. 10) were dominated by guaiacol compounds and their derivatives, characteristic of lignin degradation. The major peaks present in cellulose and xylan could not be observed for beech wood, despite their high contribution in the initial mass of the sample. K-doping induced a more significant change of the pyrograms in comparison with washing. An increase in relative intensity of peaks 33 (syringol (2,6-dimethoxyphenol)), 36 (vanillic acid), 42 (2,6-dimethoxy-4-(2-propenyl)-phenol), and 46 (4-ethoxy-2,5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde) were observed. These observations suggest that potassium influenced the pyrolysis chemistry, promoting the stabilization of larger aromatic compounds. The increased formation of PAH upon K-doping (4,5-dibenzopyrene, peak 47) is specially relevant. It highlights the relevance of the synergistic behavior of K and potential transport limitation in the pyrolysis of woody biomass [35,40,42].

3.4. Evolution of the chemical structure by *in-situ* DRIFTS

In-situ diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier-transform spectroscopy (*in-situ* DRIFTS) was applied to characterize the evolution of functional groups in the reacting solid and thus gain information about the pyrolysis chemistry. The full recorded spectra at ambient conditions for each sample is shown in Section D of the Supplementary Material (Figure D.9). The similarity between unmodified and K-activated samples was very high at room temperature, but some variations were observed due to the heterogeneity of the samples, especially those of lignin.

The evolution of the relative intensity (I_v/I_{max}) of significant absorption peaks as a function of conversion temperatures has been integrated with two-dimensional perturbation correlation infrared spectroscopy (2D-PCIS) to examine the changes in the chemical structure of the material undergoing pyrolysis. 2D-PCIS has proven to be an effective method for enhancing peak resolution (when peak overlap) and providing insights into the sequence of peak changes, thereby contributing to elucidate the reaction sequence [20,78]. The synchronous 2D-PCIS spectra provide information about which peaks change the most and in which direction, i.e., which functional groups are formed or destroyed over the course of the reaction. The asynchronous 2D-PCIS spectra provide information about which peaks correlate the most and in which sequence the changes occur [66,79]. Further information can be found in Section A of the Supplementary Material. The identification and selection of the most relevant peaks in each case were based on a combination of raw DRIFTS spectra for peak localization, synchronous 2D-PCIS spectra for identification of peaks with the most significant relative changes, and literature for peak attribution and validation. The most relevant peaks for cellulose [20,78,80–83], xylan [49,84,85],

Fig. 15. 2D-PCIS spectra of xylan (X) samples.

lignin [86–88] and beech wood [89,90] are gathered in the Section D (Table D.22) of the Supplementary Material.

3.4.1. Cellulose (C) and K-doped cellulose (C-K2)

For cellulose, a large absorption region in the wavenumber range of 3000–3700 cm^{-1} , associated with OH (hydroxyl) stretching [20,78,80,81], was observed. Peaks around 3450 cm^{-1} or higher wavenumber correspond to weakly hydrogen-bonded (H-bonded) or free OH groups [78,80,82]. As the H-bond strength increases, the OH vibration shifts to lower wavenumbers [80]. In this study, vibration signals at 3550 cm^{-1} , 3370 cm^{-1} , and 3286 cm^{-1} were identified as indicative of OH group behavior. The peak at around 3350 cm^{-1} has been clearly attributed to intramolecular H-bonding by the secondary alcohol C(3)O(3)H (O(3)H...O(5)) [78,80,81,83], while the peaks at 3286 cm^{-1} and below have been attributed to both intramolecular H-bonding by secondary alcohols (O(2)H...O(6)) [78,80,83] and intermolecular bonding by primary alcohols (O(6)H...O(3)) [80,81]. Peaks at 3370 cm^{-1} and 3286 cm^{-1} decreased with temperature, starting at around 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, with the most significant decay occurring after 350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Conversely, the peak at 3550 cm^{-1} initially increased slightly until approximately 340 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ before decreasing (see Fig. 11(a)). The synchronous (Fig. 12(a)) and asynchronous (Fig. 12(b)) 2D-PCIS spectra provide detailed insights into peak correlations and change sequences [66]. According to Noda's rules [66] for analyzing the synchronous $\Phi(3550,3370)$, $\Phi(3370,3286)$ and asynchronous $\Psi(3550,3370)$, $\Psi(3370,3286)$ cross-peaks, changes at 3370 cm^{-1} and

3286 cm^{-1} occurred first, followed by changes at 3550 cm^{-1} . This suggests that cleavage of intermolecular and intramolecular H-bonds in the OH groups, leading to weakly H-bonded and free OH groups, occurred before a strong decline of all OH groups due to dehydration reactions at higher temperatures. These findings align well with those reported by Dai et al. [20] and Leng et al. [78].

Around 2900 cm^{-1} , a distinct absorption region can be identified (see Figure D.9 in the Supplementary Material), attributed to C–H stretching [80]. In this study, vibrations at 2900 cm^{-1} and 2950 cm^{-1} were considered. The peak at 2900 cm^{-1} has been attributed to C–H stretching in glucopyranose rings, while the signal at around 2950 cm^{-1} is related to C–H asymmetric stretching in the C6-methylene of glucopyranose rings [20,78,81]. The peak at 2900 cm^{-1} decreased in relative intensity starting at around 340 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, whereas the signal at 2950 cm^{-1} initially increased before decreasing from 360 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ onward (Fig. 11(a)). The synchronous $\Phi(3550,2900)$, $\Phi(3370,2900)$, $\Phi(3286,2900)$ and asynchronous $\Psi(3550,2900)$, $\Psi(3370,2900)$, $\Psi(3286,2900)$ cross-peaks (Figs. 12(a) and 12(b)) suggest that the weakening and breaking of H-bonds occurred before the cleavage of C–H bonds in the glucopyranose rings, which preceded the loss of OH groups (dehydration reactions). The increase in C–H asymmetric stretching in the C6-methylene may indicate a link to the weakening and cleavage of intermolecular H-bonds established by the primary alcohol.

The peak at 1724 cm^{-1} is attributed to G=O stretching in saturated aldehyde carbonyls and ketones, while that at 1610 cm^{-1} is associated with C=C in conjugated alkenes [78,81]. Both peaks increased in relative intensity starting from 340 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ onward (Fig. 11(b)).

Fig. 16. 2D-PCIS spectra of K-doped xylan (X-K) samples.

The signals around 1166 cm^{-1} and 1125 cm^{-1} are attributed to C–O stretching of glycosidic bonds and C–O stretching in the glucopyranose ring, respectively [20,78,80,81]. Additionally, peaks at 1426 cm^{-1} and 1370 cm^{-1} are attributed to symmetric bending in the C6-methylene of the glucopyranose ring and to C–H bending in the glucopyranose ring, respectively [20,78]. These peaks facilitate direct comparison with lower wavenumber peaks in the 2D-PCIS spectra. Analysis of the synchronous and asynchronous spectra (Figs. 12(c) and 12(d)) indicates that the cleavage of C–H (both in C6-methylene and in the ring) and C–O (glycosidic and in the ring) bonds, as well as the formation of C=O bonds, preceded the formation of C=C bonds. The lower thermal stability shown by the signal at 1426 cm^{-1} in comparison to the signal at 2950 cm^{-1} (Figs. 11(a) and 11(b)), which should correspond to different vibration modi of C–H in the C6-methylene group of the glucopyranose ring, needs further clarification. However, if the signal at 1426 cm^{-1} is considered to track the evolution of the C6-methylene group, it could be concluded that the reduction of C–H in C6-methylene occurred predominantly before the formation of C=O bonds, while the changes in C–H (in glucopyranose ring) and in C–O (both glycosidic bond and in the glucopyranose ring) occurred more or less at the same time as the formation of C=O. It has been discussed, based on density functional theory (DFT) calculations, that dissociation of C6-methylene started to occur at low temperatures, either via Grob fragmentation without ring opening or favored by ring opening [20].

Based on these results, a mechanistic pathway for the pyrolysis of cellulose can be proposed. First, weakening of H-bonds occurred, which

constitutes a necessary initial activation step [91]. This is followed by depolymerization reactions. Based on the *in-situ*-DRIFTS results, both C–H and C–O bonds cleavage and C=O formation seem to occur approximately at the same time. This hints that both main pathways for cellulose depolymerization, glycosidic bond cleavage with further dehydration of the scission products and ring opening reactions to form light oxygenates and furans are relevant. This is consistent with the products composition obtained by Py-GC/MS, with important contribution from glucose, anhydrosugars, and dianhydrosugars (related to the first pathway), as well as by smaller compounds and furans, mainly produced through the second pathway. Reactions involving the formation of C=C bonds were slightly delayed with respect to depolymerization reactions. They may be mostly attributed to dehydration reactions of the intermediate products. The fact that most depolymerization reactions occurred together and in a relatively narrow temperature span agrees with the TGA measurements and kinetic modeling though a single, first-order high-activation energy reaction. The maximum of the devolatilization reactions as recorded by the DRIFTS analysis are slightly delayed to higher temperatures in comparison to the TGA measurements. This may be due to some thermal lag in the DRIFTS cell. The low char production for cellulose also indicates that depolymerization reactions and vaporization of the products dominated over char-formation reactions, which also explains the high endothermic character of the process.

Comparing the evolution of functional groups for cellulose (C) and K-doped cellulose (C-K2), the most obvious differences were the

Fig. 17. Evolution of selected FTIR peaks versus pyrolysis temperature.

earlier formation of C=O (starting at around 250 °C) in C-K2 and the higher relative decay of OH and C–O groups, also in C-K2 (Figs. 11(c) and 11(d)). Looking at the synchronous and asynchronous spectra for C-K2 (Fig. 13), the changes in H-bonded OH groups occurred first, followed by changes in C–H in the glucopyranose ring, occurring approximately at the same time as those of free OH groups. That is, the occurrence of dehydration and C–H cleavage reactions overlapped more than for cellulose (C). Changes in the C6-methylene of the glucopyranose ring (asymmetric stretching) were significantly milder for C-K2 in comparison to C at temperatures below 450 °C. Looking in detail to Fig. 11(c), it can be seen that the decays in weakly H-bonded/free OH groups and in C–H in glucopyranose ring were slightly delayed to higher temperatures for C-K2 in comparison to C (360 °C versus 340 °C, approximately). A similar behavior was observed for the signal at 1166 cm⁻¹ (C–O in glycosidic bonds). Opposite to cellulose, and according to the synchronous ($\Phi(1724,1370)$, $\Phi(1724,1426)$, $\Phi(1724,1166)$, $\Phi(1724,1125)$ in Fig. 13(c)) and asynchronous ($\Psi(1724,1370)$, $\Psi(1724,1426)$, $\Psi(1724,1166)$, $\Psi(1724,1125)$ in Fig. 13(d)) spectra, changes in C=O groups occurred predominantly prior to changes in C–H in the glucopyranose ring and in the C6 methoxyl group. They also preceded the changes in C–O in both in glycosidic bonds and in the glucopyranose rings. Different decay regions could be identified in the evolution of the signals at 1426 cm⁻¹, 1125 cm⁻¹, and 1370 cm⁻¹ (Fig. 11(d)). Whereas the major decay occurred in the temperature region between 340–450 °C, already a milder decay occurred at temperatures between 200–340 °C. This would explain the predominantly delayed changes in C–H and C–O compared to C=O shown by the synchronous and asynchronous spectra (major changes at higher temperatures for C–H and C–O than for C=O), but at the same time would provide the broken C–H and C–O bonds

needed for the formation of C=O bonds. The formation of C=C bonds occurred later than the formation of C=O bonds and the breakage of C–O and C–H bonds.

K-doping clearly impacted the pyrolysis mechanism, hindering the devolatilization process (more char produced), delaying the maximum devolatilization peak, and shifting the process thermochemistry from strongly endothermic to mildly exothermic (Figs. 1(b), 1(c), and 1(d)). K-promoted enhancement of dehydration reactions, leading to more cross-linking reactions, and thus char formation and higher exothermicity, is a well-known effect of doping with alkali elements [40,44]. Looking at the decay of the main depolymerization-related functional groups, two regions could be identified (Fig. 11(d)), compared to the more overlapped conversion for cellulose (Fig. 11(b)). This agrees with the devolatilization curves recorded in the TGA analysis, delayed in time and with broader fw (full width of the devolatilization curve) for C-K2. Based on the DRIFTS results (Fig. 13(d)), it could be concluded that the presence of K promoted C–O ring opening reactions, enhancing the formation of C=O in the form of aldehydes and ketones [91]. An increase in the ring opening reactions by weakening of the epoxy-ether bond, rendering the glycosidic bond more susceptible to ring-opening reactions than to depolymerization, has been also discussed by Zhao et al. [91]. This would also be consistent with the shift of the hydrogen at C5 position to form C(5)=O, as proposed by Dai et al. [20]. It would also agree with the low production of sugars and anhydrosugars, as well as with the inhibition of dianhydrosugars, in favor of light oxygenates and furans, as shown by Py-GC/MS. The production of levoglucosan was still relevant, supporting its formation from glycosidic bond cleavage of non-reducing ends [12].

Fig. 18. Evolution of selected FTIR peaks versus pyrolysis temperature.

3.4.2. Xylan and K-doped xylan

The evolution of functional groups in xylan presents several characteristic regions (see Fig. 14), coincident with the multi-step devolatilization scheme often attributed to hemicellulose [92,93] and with the TGA measurements reported in this study (Fig. 2). Similar qualitative behavior was also reported by Dai et al. when analyzing xylan [49]. The signals at around 3600 cm^{-1} were the strongest ones (see auto-peaks in Fig. 15(a)). Therefore, the signals at 3640 cm^{-1} and 3590 cm^{-1} were used to track the evolution of OH groups, corresponding to free OH or weak H-bonded OH groups [49,78,80,82]. Both signals behaved differently though. The signal at 3590 cm^{-1} first increased up to $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, followed by a decrease and a second increase at temperatures higher than $250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. From $360\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ on, a continuous decrease took place (Fig. 14(a)). This behavior would be consistent with the weakening

and cleavage of H-bonds, forming weakly bonded free hydroxyls at low temperatures, followed by the reduction of these groups via dehydration reactions at higher temperatures. However, the signal at 3640 cm^{-1} directly decreased with increasing temperature until $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, followed by a mild increase and a strong decrease at temperatures above $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. This high wavenumber is not typically reported in hemicellulose [49,84,85]. It may come from free OH groups in lignin or extractives residuals still present in the xylan [49]. The absorption signals at around 2900 cm^{-1} are attributed to C–H vibrations [49,84,85]. In particular, the signal at around 2990 cm^{-1} is attributed to CH_3 in O-acetyl and 4-O-methyl-uronic acid [49], as well as to C–H in alkenes [85]. The signals at 2920 cm^{-1} and 2890 cm^{-1} are attributed to CH_2 at C5 in xylose [49] and to C–H stretching in xylopyranose rings [49], respectively. The three signals globally increased in intensity

Fig. 19. 2D-PCIS spectra of washed beech wood (B-W) samples.

with the pyrolysis process (Fig. 14(a)). Dai et al. reported a decrease of the three signals with pyrolysis temperature, with intermediate mild increases coincident with the increase in OH groups, attributed to the degradation of the carbon skeleton [49]. Wang et al. on the contrary, observed a continuous decrease of the signal at 2920 cm^{-1} and a continuous increase of the signal at 2990 cm^{-1} with pyrolysis temperature, the latter attributed to the formation of alkenes from alkanes [85]. The signals at 1420 cm^{-1} and 1380 cm^{-1} are also attributed to CH_2 in xylopyranose ring [49,85] and to the symmetric vibration of CH_3 in O-acetyl and 4-O-methyl-uronic acid [85], respectively. They both decreased overall with pyrolysis temperature following a pattern similar to the decrease of OH groups (Fig. 14(b)), in good agreement with the results shown by Dai et al. [49], and opposite to the behavior observed for the signals around 2900 cm^{-1} . This may indicate that the latter signals are masked by other phenomena, potentially induced by the significant content in inorganic species. Therefore, the signals at 1420 cm^{-1} and 1380 cm^{-1} were used in the present work to analyze the behavior of C–H bonds. The signals at 1160 cm^{-1} and 981 cm^{-1} are attributed to C–O in glycosidic bonds and C–O in the xylopyranose ring, respectively [20,49,78]. The evolutions of these signals, together with C–H signals, indicate xylan depolymerization. G=O (1730 cm^{-1} [49]) and aromatic C=C (1540 cm^{-1} [85]) signals clearly increased with pyrolysis temperature from approximately $200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ on. The evolution of relative intensities (Fig. 14(b)) showed a decrease in the signal of C–O in glycosidic bonds and free OH groups at temperatures below $200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, whereas the signals attributed to aromatic C=C, C–H in CH_3 ,

and in CH_2 , OH groups and C–O in the xylopyranose ring, and weakly-bonded or free OH groups increased. The cleavage of C–O and OH led to the formation of C=C and C=O to a lesser extent. The increase in OH signal at low temperatures can be explained by the cleavage of H-bonds. The increase in C–H in CH_3 and CH_2 , as well as of C–O in the xylopyranose ring, also shown by Dai et al. [49], may be attributed to a less stable structure and even the formation of some intermediates, enhanced by the complex and heterogeneous structure of xylan, after the initial depolymerization reactions.

Between $200\text{--}250\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, a decrease in the relative intensity of CH_2/CH_3 , C–O in the xylopyranose ring, and OH groups occurred. This was coincident with the first peak in the devolatilization of xylan and accompanied by a constant increase in G=O and C=C signals. At temperatures above $250\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, mainly a decrease in C–O from glycosidic bonds took place, accompanied by the further formation of C=O and C=C bonds. At temperatures above $320\text{--}350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, cleavage of CH_2/CH_3 , C–O in xylopyranose ring, and OH groups dominated again the evolution of functional groups. At around $340\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the formation of C=O and C=C also reached its maximum, followed by a mild decrease. Due to these different phases, it is more difficult to interpret the synchronous and asynchronous correlation spectra (Figs. 15 and 16). Overall, cleavage of C–O in xylopyranose ring occurred predominantly prior to the formation of C=O ($\Phi(1730,981)$, $\Psi(1730,981)$) and C=C ($\Phi(1540,981)$, $\Psi(1540,981)$) and to the loss of OH groups in the xylopyranose ring through dehydration reactions ($\Phi(1070,981)$, $\Psi(1070,981)$). The formation of C=O predominantly preceded the formation of C=C bonds

Fig. 20. 2D-PCIS spectra of beech wood (B) samples.

($\Phi(1730,1540)$, $\Psi(1730,1540)$) as well. Changes in C–H in CH_3 groups also occurred predominantly prior to the formation of C=O and C=C, while changes in C–H in CH_2 occurred mainly after those in C=O.

Addition of K had a significant impact on the evolution of the functional groups. First, the formation of free or weakly H-bonded OH groups (signal 3590 cm^{-1}) was significantly damped by the addition of K. The signal at higher wavenumbers presented a more similar qualitative behavior to xylan, although with higher relative intensities at higher temperatures. This suggests that addition of K hindered the cleavage of H-bonds and the dehydration reactions during pyrolysis of xylan. The formation of C=O bonds was also delayed by about 100°C compared to xylan, to temperatures above 300°C . K-addition also shifted the cleavage of glycosidic bonds to higher temperatures, while it promoted the cleavage of C–O and C–H in xylopyranose ring, as well as the cleavage of C–H in CH_3 .

The evolution of functional groups could be qualitatively correlated to the multi-step devolatilization recorded for xylan and the shift to lower temperatures of the major devolatilization peak upon addition of K, consistent with the promotion of cleavage reactions of C–O and C–H in xylopyranose ring and C–H in CH_3 groups. This resulted also in a more concentrated exothermic region. Xylan is often used as model compound for hemicellulose in beech wood. However, it has the disadvantage that does not fully reproduce the composition of hemicellulose and that it typically shows a high content in inorganic species, derived from the extraction process. Despite this, the behavior of xylan showed the two-step devolatilization process also captured by the TGA analysis.

The devolatilization of xylan occurred at lower temperature compared to pseudo-hemicellulose in beech wood, probably due to the presence of cellulose and lignin in the wood, providing more stability and thus delaying the devolatilization. Furthermore, the inorganic content in commercial xylan could also promote earlier devolatilization.

3.4.3. Lignin and K-doped lignin

Signals at 3650 cm^{-1} , 3540 cm^{-1} , and 3475 cm^{-1} were considered to analyze the evolution of OH groups during the pyrolysis of lignin, as seen in Fig. 17(a) and Fig. 17(c). The signals at 3540 cm^{-1} and 3475 cm^{-1} first increased below 200°C , probably due to weakening and cleavage of H-bonds, forming more free OH groups. From 200°C on, a significant decrease, especially in the signal at 3475 cm^{-1} , occurred, accompanied by the formation of C=O (1810 cm^{-1} in esters [86]) up to 300°C . At higher temperatures, these C=O groups decomposed further in two relevant stages. The OH signal at 3650 cm^{-1} increased significantly with temperature from 200°C on, likely due to the formation of phenolic alcohols [89]. At temperatures above 300°C a decrease in intensity occurred followed by a rather stable behavior at temperatures above 400°C . The signals at 1600 cm^{-1} and 1510 cm^{-1} (Figs. 17(b) and 17(d)) are attributed to C–C vibration in aromatic rings and to C=C vibration in conjugated alkenes, respectively [87]. The signal at around 1275 cm^{-1} is attributed to aromatic ether C–O–C [88]. Noteworthy is the fact that for these signals the relative intensity decreased at the same time.

K-addition resulted in an initial loss of OH groups (3475 cm^{-1}) at lower temperatures, followed by a higher loss up to 350°C . It

Fig. 21. 2D-PCIS spectra of K-doped beech wood (B-K) samples.

also reduced the cleavage of C=O groups at higher temperatures and shifted the formation of phenolic-OH to higher temperatures. Furthermore, this modification reduced the loss of C=O groups in ketones and shifted the loss of C=O groups in aldehydes to higher temperatures. K-addition clearly impacted the reactions involving OH groups and C=O bonds. However, this impact was not clearly replicated in the products composition and in the devolatilization behavior of lignin.

3.4.4. Washed beech, beech, and K-doped beech

The IR absorption behavior of beech wood is a combination of those of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. The signals at 3550 cm^{-1} , 3370 cm^{-1} , and 3286 cm^{-1} , seen in Figs. 18(a), 18(c) and 18(e), were selected to follow the evolution of OH groups, corresponding to weakly H-bonded or free OH groups (also in phenols) and to intramolecular/intermolecular H-bonding [89,90]. The selected signals were also coincident with the ones considered for cellulose. The observed behavior for washed beech wood (B-W) and beech wood (B) was similar to the one for cellulose for OH groups with intermolecular and intramolecular H-bonds. That is, the signal at 3286 cm^{-1} decreased the most with increasing temperature, followed by the signal at 3370 cm^{-1} . This suggests that intermolecular H-bonds with C(6) alcohols and intramolecular H-bonds with C(2) alcohols were first cleaved, followed by intramolecular H-bonds with C(3) alcohols. However, no clear increase in the relative intensity of weakly H-bonded or free OH groups

(3550 cm^{-1}) was detected. Looking at the cross-peaks, (3550,3370), (3550,3286), (3370,3286), (3286,2935), (2935,2890), (2970,2935) in the synchronous and asynchronous 2D-PCIS (Figs. 19–21), it could be concluded that the cleavage of intermolecular and intramolecular H-bonds occurred predominantly before the cleavage of C–H in the methylene group, in the sugar rings, and in $-\text{CH}_3$. C–H in the sugar ring showed lower thermal stability than C–H in CH_2 and $-\text{CH}_3$, with similar stability. C–H cleavage occurred also predominantly before the breakage of weakly H-bonded or free OH groups by dehydration reactions. These results suggest that changes in C–H in sugar rings and, potentially, the opening of sugar rings occurred before removal of CH_2 in sugar rings (cellulose and hemicellulose) and before demethoxylation of lignin [89]. Although these reactions occurred at high temperatures, mostly above $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The signal at 3055 cm^{-1} is attributed to aromatic C–H [89]. It increased significantly with temperature, consistent with the formation of aromatic rings during the pyrolysis process. For washed beech wood, its increase started at around $450\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Higher K content shifted this temperature to lower values, starting at around $350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for B and B-K.

Different levels of K impacted the H-bond cleavage and the dehydration reactions at different stages of the pyrolysis process. For B-W, the signal at 3286 cm^{-1} decreased in a monotonic manner between approximately $120\text{--}450\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. At temperatures above $450\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the loss rate increased until around $550\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The signal 3370 cm^{-1} decreased

also mildly up to 450 °C, followed by an increase in loss rate until 550 °C, as for the signal at 3286 cm⁻¹. However, the signal at 3550 cm⁻¹ remained rather constant and with high relative intensities ($0.9 < I_v/I_m < 1$), followed by a mild decrease. In the case of B (natural K content in beech wood), the signal at 3286 cm⁻¹ experienced a decay between 120–600 °C in three main steps. The loss of the signal in the lower temperature ranges was higher than for B-W. The loss of 3370 cm⁻¹ and 3550 cm⁻¹ signals was also more dramatic than for B-W. Upon K-addition, an initial decrease in the signal at 3286 cm⁻¹ occurred between 100–125 °C, followed by an increase up to 200 °C. From 350 °C on, a steeper loss rate was observed until 500 °C. This behavior was reproduced by the signal at 3370 cm⁻¹, excluding the first initial decay. The signal at 3550 cm⁻¹ mirrored the signal at 3286 cm⁻¹, suggesting that broken H-bonds led to free OH groups and a decrease in free OH groups at these low temperatures would be related to the formation of new H-bonds rather than to dehydration reactions. The signal then increased mildly up to 350 °C, followed by a steeper decrease until around 500 °C. These results indicate that K promoted the cleavage of H-bonds and the dehydration reactions during beech wood pyrolysis. The cleavage of C–H bonds was tracked through the signals at 2935 cm⁻¹ (C–H₂ in methylene group in sugar ring) and 2890 cm⁻¹ (C–H stretching in sugar ring) [89], in good agreement with the signals reported for cellulose and xylan, and the signal at 2970 cm⁻¹ (C–H stretching in -CH₃) [89]. For B-W both signals remained constant or even increased a bit in relative intensity until 300 °C, followed by a mild decay up to 450 °C and a much stronger decay afterwards (Figs. 18(a), 18(c), and 18(e)). The results suggest that these bonds remained rather stable in B-W. In B, similar behavior was observed up to 300 °C. However, the decay at higher temperatures was faster than for B-W. For B-K there was a mild decay of the signal related to CH₂ stretching in the temperature range of 100–120 °C, analogous to the behavior reported for the signal 3286 cm⁻¹. Since the latter is attributed, among others, to intermolecular H-bonds by the primary alcohols in C(6) and the signal at 2935 cm⁻¹ is attributed to C–H asymmetric stretching in the CH₂ group in C(6), the results suggest that the addition of K first attacked this group in the sugar ring. The decrease at temperatures above 300 °C, especially for the C–H stretching in the sugar ring, was also higher for the K-doped samples, indicating a catalytic effect.

The impact of K in the low wavenumber region was even higher (Figs. 18(b), 18(d), and 18(f)). Signals at 1750 cm⁻¹, 1660 cm⁻¹, and 1595 cm⁻¹ are attributed to C=O stretching (esters, acids), C=C stretching in linear unconjugated alkenes, and C–C stretching in the aromatic skeleton, respectively [89]. Furthermore, the signals at 1428 cm⁻¹ and 1378 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to C–H bending in C6-methylene and C–H bending in the sugar rings, respectively [20,78]. But they can be also attributed to -CH₃ from lignin. Finally, the signal at 1166 cm⁻¹ is attributed to C–O stretching [89], either from C–O–C glycosidic bonds in cellulose [20,78], or phenol groups [89]. All these signals decreased with increasing temperature for washed beech wood (B-W), mainly between 300–500 °C. The cleavage of these functional groups is responsible for the devolatilization of beech wood. At temperatures higher than 500 °C further formation of C–C bonds in the aromatic skeleton occurred. Furthermore, from 400 °C on, the signal at 845 cm⁻¹ also increased, associated with C–H bending in aryl structures [89]. This is consistent with the formation of aromatic species and with the condensation of the solid structure. Opposite to cellulose and xylan, C=O and C=C bonds decreased with increasing temperature. These functional groups are present in beech wood through lignin and they decrease as the devolatilization of lignin progresses (see Fig. 17). Reduction of C=C in unconjugated alkenes, aromatic C–C, C–H in CH₂, and C–H in sugar ring occurred predominantly prior to decrease in C=O groups. Cleavage of C–O in sugar ring and formation of substituted aryl structures occurred predominantly after the reduction in C=O groups. The reduction of C=C and aromatic C–C happened mainly before the cleavage of C–H bonds.

With higher content in K (beech wood), the behavior of aromatic C–C groups and unconjugated C=C alkenes (see Fig. 18(d)) changed significantly with respect to washed beech wood (see Fig. 18(b)). The evolution of the relative intensity of aromatic C–C remained between $0.9 < I_v/I_m < 1$, with higher values above 300 °C. This indicates that the reactions leading to the formation of aromatic C–C in comparison to those inducing its loss were greatly enhanced with K. This was even more clear upon K-addition (see Fig. 18(f)). Similar behavior was observed for unconjugated C=C alkenes. Higher levels of K also hindered the cleavage of C–H bonds while it did not impact reactions involving the loss of C=O.

Based on the evolution of functional groups, it could be concluded that K-doping impacted the pyrolysis of beech wood the most, due to the different impact on its macrocomponents. This is also reflected by the devolatilization behavior, the thermochemistry, and the products composition. The evolution of functional groups in beech wood is a summation of their evolution in the different macrocomponents. This results in diverging behaviors for some groups between beech wood and its macrocomponents. For example, C=O was mainly formed in cellulose due to different depolymerization reactions, but it decreased in beech wood, driven by its decrease in lignin. The composition of the products was dominated by those coming from lignin, whereas the devolatilization behavior was dominated by hemicellulose and cellulose and the changes in thermochemistry resembled most closely those of cellulose. Consequently, gaining a deeper understanding on the mechanistic behavior of wood pyrolysis requires not only the understanding of the behavior of its macrocomponents but also of their interaction at a multiple level.

4. Conclusions

The combined impact of potassium (K) and mild transport limitations on the pyrolytic behavior of beech wood, as well as on its macrocomponents, was studied combining TGA/DSC analysis, kinetic modeling, *in-situ* DRIFTS, and Py-GC/MS. Commercial compounds were used as model macrocomponents. Mild intra-particle transport limitations were addressed by using initial masses of 5 mg and 20 mg. Mild external transport limitations were imposed by using a lid on the TGA crucible with 5 mg of sample. Different K contents were achieved by washing (deionized water) and K-doping (solutions of KCl) the samples.

The effect of K was most pronounced in beech wood, cellulose, and xylan, but in a different manner. It significantly altered the thermochemistry of cellulose and beech wood pyrolysis, changing the process from globally endothermic to exothermic under intra-sample transport limitations. In contrast, xylan and lignin remained exothermic under the same conditions. K also influenced the devolatilization behavior by shifting the peak devolatilization rate to higher temperatures for cellulose and lower temperatures for xylan and beech wood, while increasing the overlap during devolatilization for beech wood. Kinetic analysis revealed complex interactions between K and transport limitations, impacting global pyrolysis kinetic parameters differently across materials, levels of potassium, and transport regimes. To better understand these effects on beech wood through its macrocomponents, a five-parallel reaction model (two reactions for hemicellulose, one for cellulose, and two for lignin) was developed. According to the model, K-addition reduced the activation energy in the devolatilization of cellulose, and hemicellulose, while it had little impact on lignin. Comparing the pseudo-components obtained from the model and the commercial macrocomponents used, the pseudo-cellulose behavior agreed acceptably well with the commercial macrocomponent. Deviations increased with higher content in K, which could be due to the lack of perfect matching between the K content in cellulose and in beech wood, but also due to different interactions between K and the macrocomponents in the wood, including thermochemistry. In the case of pseudo-hemicellulose and xylan, the agreement was worse, mainly due to the earlier decomposition of commercial xylan,

potentially related to the higher content in inorganics species and the lack more stable structures such as cellulose and lignin.

To better understand how K affected beech wood and its macrocomponents, *in-situ* DRIFTS was combined with Py-GC/MS. This approach allows to gather more detailed information about the mechanistic pathways involved, which can help clarify how each component contributes to the pyrolytic behavior of beech wood when influenced by K. In this case, the impact of transport limitations was not addressed.

Qualitative analysis of functional groups evolution revealed that K significantly influenced the pyrolysis of beech wood, xylan, and cellulose, in that order. Combination with Py-GC/MS results showed that K promoted ring opening and dehydration reactions in cellulose and xylan. In the case of cellulose, although changes in functional groups were limited in comparison to xylan and beech wood, they led to notable shifts in product distribution, hindering sugar formation upon K-addition. For xylan, the impact on the evolution of functional groups was more pronounced than on product distribution. Lignin showed no significant changes due to its high inorganic content. The behavior of beech wood reflected the combined effects of its macrocomponents. Overall, this study offers a detailed picture on the combined impact of K and mild transport limitations on the pyrolysis behavior of beech wood and its macrocomponents, including information about the *in-situ* evolution of functional groups and pyrolysis products, which contribute to understand the pyrolysis chemistry. A comprehensive understanding of wood pyrolysis requires examining both individual component behaviors and their interactions at multiple levels.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Juan Jesús Rico: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Andrea Dernbecher:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **José María de la Rosa:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Liane Hilfert:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Formal analysis. **Hernán Almuina-Villar:** Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Nora Kulak:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision. **Sergio Lucia:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Alba Dieguez-Alonso:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2025.107201>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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